

Country Perspectives on Improving Technical Assistance in the Health Sector

Kanagat N, Chauffour J, Ilunga JF, Yuma Ramazani S, Ovuoraye Ajjwohwodoma JJP, Ibrahim Anas-Kolo S, Maryjane O, Onuekwusi N *et al.* (2021). Gates Open Research.

Extended data— Re-Imagining Technical Assistance project timeline and co-creation phases

Activity	Objective	Timeline
Project start date		April 12, 2018
Scoping trips	The team conducted field visits with the goal of understanding the stakeholder and healthcare landscapes in both countries. Interviews were conducted as well as site visits to general and specialty hospitals (DRC) and sitting in on the Child Health Technical Working Group meeting (Nigeria). The outputs were draft maps of the country stakeholders and healthcare system, as well as general themes and insights which were used to inform the first co-creation workshop ("intent workshop").	DRC and Nigeria: November 2018
Stakeholder interviews (<i>phone/virtual</i>)	The team conducted one-on-one interviews through Skype and in person to gather participant perspectives on technical assistance (TA), its benefits and challenges, the implications of the challenging aspects, the vision for how TA could be improved and taken forward within the country.	Nigeria: January - February 2019
BMGF/Government of Nigeria visit	The team visited Abuja to meet with the country office of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF), several TA providers and representatives of different departments at the Federal Ministry of Health. Aim of this visit was to socialize the initiative among key stakeholders and invite participation in the process through conducting interviews and participation at the upcoming workshop.	Nigeria: March 22-29, 2019
Intent workshop	The team established a shared understanding of the current TA challenges and opportunities faced by various actors in the health system, the project drivers for change, and what success looks like from all key stakeholders.	DRC: March 2019 Nigeria: June 24-25, 2019
Conceptualization, prototypes, and testing workshop	The team fostered collective ownership of the redesign process. From the concepts developed during the intent workshop, four were prioritized and further developed through ideation, prototyping, and testing by target groups.	DRC: May 5-12, 2019
Reframing and alignment	Missing perspectives on TA were gathered through stakeholder interviews and secondary research, results from all prior work were merged and reorganized, and opportunity areas reviewed. The team generated themes for design principles.	Both countries: July to October 2019

Remote co-creation team meetings	The team held remote meetings with the country co-creation teams in order to update them on the project's status and work completed during the "reframing and alignment" phase.	DRC: September 2019 Nigeria: August 2019
Design sprint 1	The study team interviewed public- and private-sector central-level stakeholders working in any capacity on TA or with TA providers. Interviews centered on their perception of the strengths and weaknesses of TA, recommendations for new models of TA, behavior change in the context of improving TA, and sharing promising TA practices they may have encountered. Conversations around TA often centered on the relationship between the TA providers and the recipient country. Findings were consolidated into decks developed by Sonder Collective available at https://www.childhealthtaskforce.org/countries/drc and https://www.childhealthtaskforce.org/countries/nigeria	Both countries: November 2019
Design sprint 2	The study team selected and refined strategies for re-imagining TA for each opportunity area and consolidated design principles for good TA. The concepts were prioritized and refined and a roadmap for change created.	DRC: December 2019
Integration workshop	The co-creation team revisited and integrated strategies from each opportunity area developed in the design sprints into a coherent set of actionable principles and strategies for re-imagining TA. The roadmap for change was refined and an action plan for country implementation of the recommendations developed by the co-creation team before being presented to a larger group of stakeholders.	Nigeria: January 2020 DRC: March 2020
Validation meeting	A small group of the co-creation team and external experts reviewed the final report from the Integration workshop. The final report aligned the project findings with current national strategies and incorporated feedback received from the Secretary General (SG). An official Ministry of Health document was created and validated at a meeting for submission to the SG.	DRC: April 2020
Project end date		September 30, 2020